

Card-based reflection activity

- **Hardware**
 - Production
 - Use
 - Waste disposal
- **Software**
 - Production
 - Use
 - Waste disposal
- **Content**
- **Working conditions**

Supply chain

The supply chain

<https://www.greenbiz.com/article/child-labor-might-be-hidden-your-smartphones-supply-chain>

Rare earths + precious metals mining

Precious metals

A BREAKDOWN OF THE CRITICAL METALS IN A SMARTPHONE

Some vital metals used to build these devices are considered at risk due to geological scarcity, geopolitical issues or trade policy. This infographic details the critical metals that you carry in your pocket.

ALKALI METAL | ALKALINE EARTH | TRANSITION METAL | BASIC METAL | LANTHANOID

TOUCH SCREEN
It contains a thin layer of indium tin oxide, highly conductive and transparent, allowing the screen to function as a touch screen.

DISPLAY
The display contains several rare earth elements. Small quantities are used to produce the colors on the liquid crystal display. Some give the screen its glow.

ELECTRONICS
Nickel is used in electrical connections. Gallium is used in semiconductors. Tantalum is the major component of micro capacitors, used for filtering and frequency tuning.

CASING
Nickel reduces electromagnetic interference. Magnesium alloys are superior at electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding.

BATTERY
The majority of smartphones use lithium-ion batteries.

MICROPHONE, SPEAKERS, VIBRATION UNIT
Nickel is used in the microphone diaphragm (that vibrates in response to sound waves). Alloys containing neodymium, praseodymium and gadolinium are used in the magnets contained in the speaker and microphone. Neodymium, terbium and dysprosium are used in the vibration unit.

Source: University of Birmingham

ELEMENTS
elements.visualcapitalist.com

The Earth's natural resources power our everyday lives. VC Elements breaks down the building blocks of the universe.

We live in a material world.

smartphone composition (weight%)

metal content (weight%)

* (% of total metal value)

(c) BGR/PrinzMayer

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0301420720301392>
<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/08/this-visualization-breaks-down-the-metals-in-a-smartphone/>

World

Dozens missing, 14 dead after illegal gold mine collapses in Venezuela

Miner who survived collapse describes terrifying conditions at the scene

The Associated Press · Posted: Feb 21, 2024 8:29 PM EST | Last Updated: February 22

People gather at the bank of Guacara River Port on Wednesday while waiting for information on the miners.

(Reuters TV/Reuters)

<https://www.cbc.ca/news/world/venezuela-gold-mine-collapse-1.7121916>

Mining of rare earth metals

<https://www.ethicalconsumer.org/technology/global-supply-chain-mobile-phone>

<https://www.dw.com/de/der-kobaltbergbau-im-kongo-wirft-schatten-auf-die-tr%C3%A4ume-von-elektromobilit%C3%A4t/a-41369952>

Material costs

What does the material of a smartphone cost?

Example iPhone 6s

components	price in \$
display / touchscreen / glass	52,50
battery	4,50
Taptic Engine	10,00
mainboard with processor	35,00
storage	22,50
cameras	22,50
other components	84,50
manufacturing	4,50
	236,00 \$ (etwa 209 €)

info. **Bild** Quelle: IHS-Analyse

<https://www.bild.de/digital/smartphone-und-tablet/iphone-6s/was-kostet-das-iphone-6s-plus-42922636.bild.html>

Subsidy

What is a subsidy?

→ In the IT sector, the current focus is on subsidies for chips and semiconductors

<https://www.handelsblatt.com/technik/it-internet/elektronik-abhaengigkeit-von-asien-beunruhigt-deutsche-unternehmen/28948946.html>

How do I know which smartphones are subsidized?

SAMSUNG Galaxy A54 5G 128 GB Awesome Graphite Dual SIM

Displaydiagonale
16.31 cm / 6.4 Zoll

Speicherkapazität
128 GB

Betriebssystem
Android 13.0, One UI 5.1, KNOX 3.9

Prozessor
Exynos 1380 (S5E8835)

LVP 489,-

348,74

inkl. MwSt, versandkostenfrei
Bezahle in 12 Raten à 30,57 € (eff. Zins, P.a. 9,9%)**
Gesamtpreis 366,84 €

- Online verfügbar
Lieferung 22.09.2023 - 25.09.2023
- Abholung
Bitte wählen Sie einen Markt aus **Markt auswählen**

XIAOMI Redmi A2 32 GB Black Dual SIM

Displaydiagonale
16.57 cm / 6.52 Zoll

Speicherkapazität
32 GB

Betriebssystem
Android (Go edition)

Prozessor
MediaTek Helio G36

LVP 499,98

79,99

inkl. MwSt, versandkostenfrei

- Online verfügbar
Lieferung 22.09.2023 - 25.09.2023
- Abholung
Bitte wählen Sie einen Markt aus **Markt auswählen**

APPLE iPhone 13 128 GB Mitternacht Dual SIM

Displaydiagonale
15.4 cm / 6.1 Zoll

Speicherkapazität
128 GB

Betriebssystem
iOS 15

Prozessor
A15 Bionic Chip

729,-

inkl. MwSt, versandkostenfrei
Bezahle in 24 Raten à 33,46 € (eff. Zins, P.a. 9,9%)**
Gesamtpreis 803,04 €

- Online verfügbar
Lieferung 22.09.2023 - 25.09.2023
- Abholung
Bitte wählen Sie einen Markt aus **Markt auswählen**

<https://www.techwalls.com/production-costs-of-smartphones/>

<https://www.investopedia.com/financial-edge/0912/the-cost-of-making-an-iphone.aspxn>

Waste

Waste

<https://www.trendingtopics.eu/global-e-waste-monitor-so-viel-elektroschrott-wie-noch-nie/>
<https://www.cbsnews.com/news/the-tragic-cost-of-e-waste-and-new-efforts-to-recycle/>

Production

Production

<https://de.serlo.org/politik/79248/herstellung-eines-smartphones>

<https://www.notebookcheck.com/Xiaomi-Neue-Auftragshersteller-in-Indien-Steigerung-der-Smartphone-Produktion.524475.0.html>

8 DECENT WORK AND
ECONOMIC GROWTH

Health

3 GOOD HEALTH
AND WELL-BEING

Eye diseases, psychological problems, postural damage, psychological and physical effects on employees

InNoWest

<https://www.androidauthority.com/owning-smartphone-human-environment-cost-656030/>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC775532/>
<https://www.news-medical.net/health/Mental-Health-in-a-Digitalized-Workplace.aspx>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7366948/>
<https://next.ergo.com/en/NWOW/2022/digitalisation-occupational-health-and-safety-OHS-virtual-augmented-reality-VR-AR-Home-Office-remote-video-conferencing-health-wearables.html>
[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/733986/IPOL_STU\(2022\)733986_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/733986/IPOL_STU(2022)733986_EN.pdf)

Data transmission

The evolution of website size

<https://www.greentelligent.website/blog/co2-footprint/>
<https://www.keycdn.com/support/the-growth-of-web-page-size>

Software use, websites

What is the "CO2 weight" of a website?

Minimal Carbon Site 32MB:
<https://karlsruhedigital.minimalcarbon.site>

<https://karlsruhe.digital> 635MB

Reducing the energy consumption of websites:

- using environmentally friendly websites (i.e. with little multimedia content)
- no dynamic content, such as videos on autoplay or dynamic web fonts

<https://www.greentelligent.website/blog/co2-footprint/>

Content moderation

Content moderation in social media

InNoWest

Work leads to:

- Trauma → since all possible cases are seen (sexual abuse of children, rape, torture, bestiality, beheadings, suicide and murder)
- Worldwide distribution of the work due to different languages and cheap labor in other countries
- The work experience of the content moderators is not transferable to other fields of work → a change is almost impossible

<https://www.theverge.com/2019/6/19/18681845/facebook-moderator-interviews-video-trauma-ptsd-cognizant-tampa>

<https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-42920554>

<https://www.cnet.com/tech/tech-industry/facebook-content-moderators-are-suffering-from-ptsd-claims-lawsuit/>

<https://restofworld.org/2024/content-moderators-jobs-pakistan/>

Fake news

Quelle: Facebook, <https://bit.ly/3yIXd9I> [Screenshot am 13.07.2021 | Education Innovation Lab], Bildnachweis/ Foto: Arbeitsvorlagen A5

21. August 2016 · 14 · 8 Kommentare · 23 Mal geteilt

Kirche in München, sechs Neubürger urinieren an das christliche Gotteshaus. TEILEN das auch der letzte Gutmensch diese Sauerei mitbekommt. Respektlos und traurig, bin sprachlos. Stellt euch vor was die mit uns machen würden wenn wir selbiges an einer Moschee tun ?

14 · 8 Kommentare · 23 Mal geteilt

Gefällt mir · Kommentieren · Teilen

Relevanteste zuerst

Nach der Tradition der orthodoxen Christen in Eritrea und Äthiopien gehen die Gläubigen oft nicht in die Kirche hinein, sondern beten draußen vor der Kirche. Sie lehnen sich an die Wand des Gotteshauses und beten. Die Männer auf diesem Bild beten gera... **Mehr ansehen**

Gefällt mir · Antworten · 1 J.

1 Antwort

Die Männer pinkeln nicht, sie beten.

Gefällt mir · Antworten · 4 J.

Ich habe Anstand und Respekt gelernt, aber keinen "Menschen" gegenüber, die es unserer Kultur nicht entgegenbringen.

Gefällt mir · Antworten · 4 J.

Church desecration or fake news?

Search engine

What makes a search engine sustainable?

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Hosting

- Co2 neutral
- Based on renewable energies (solar, hydropower)

Profits

- Are donated to innovative, social & charitable causes
- Are invested in environmental protection
- Planting of trees

Data protection

- No collection of user data
- Encryption of search queries
- No cookies, no tracking tools
- Anonymous search

ECOSIA

GOOD

ekoru

lilo

<https://zeit---geist.de/magazin/nachhaltige-gruene-suchmaschinen/>

Click Worker

Click Worker

InNoWest

taskrabbit

Services Sign up / Log in Become a Tasker

Assembly service provided for
IKEA

Book trusted help for home tasks

What do you need help with?

Assembly Mounting Moving Cleaning Outdoor Help Home Repairs Painting Trending

General Furniture Assembly IKEA Assembly Crib Assembly PAX Assembly Bookshelf Assembly Desk Assembly

Typical „Task Rabbit“ tasks in app usage are:

- Tagging
- Product descriptions
- Translations
- ...

<https://www.taskrabbit.com/>

Cloud

What is a cloud?

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Router

Modem

Internet provider

Data is being stored in the cloud.

Data/data centers

Network cable

<https://coolinfographics.com/blog/2016/4/11/what-are-data-centers.html>

How are data centers related to sustainability?

InNoWest

<https://dallasinnovates.com/compass-datacenters-and-schneider-electric-partner-in-red-oak-to-build-prefab-data-center-infrastructure/>
<https://www.simslifecycle.com/infographics/data-centers/>

3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Doom Scrolling

7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY

6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION

12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

What is doom scrolling and how does it relate to sustainability?

Doom scrolling not only has an impact on your psyche but also consumes...

233.38 gram CO2

28.15 liters of water

2187.9 mAh

= is a phenomenon of constantly scrolling or surfing through social media and the like to keep up to date with the latest news (and especially bad news)

With an average Internet use of 204 minutes per day.

<https://hsb-akademie.de/doomscrolling-problem-der-digitalisierten-neuzeit-und-wie-sie-es-ueberwinden/>
<https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/168069/umfrage/taegliche-internetnutzung-durch-jugendliche/>

AI assistant

The anatomy of a voice assistant

<https://www.theverge.com/2018/9/9/17832124/ai-artificial-intelligence-supply-chain-anatomy-of-ai-kate-crawford-interview>

What does an AI assistant have to do with sustainability?

InNoWest

AI WATER FOOTPRINT
The researchers noted that for a simple conversation of roughly 20-50 questions and answers
ChatGPT needs to “drink”
A 500 ML BOTTLE OF WATER

Researchers warn that the figures may multiply several times over for the recently launched GPT-4 AI system, which boasts a larger model size.

The paper is yet to be peer reviewed

NEWS 18
creative

<https://www.moneycontrol.com/news/photos/technology/thirsty-ai-chatgpt-drinks-staggering-amount-of-water-to-answer-50-questions-10442101-2.html>

Influencer Economy

3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION

Influencer economy - blessing or curse?

InNoWest

<https://omr.com/de/daily/creator-economy>

<https://www.theguardian.com/fashion/2022/feb/24/hustle-and-hype-the-truth-about-the-influencer-economy>